

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PHENOMENON OF ETHNIC IDENTITY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIALOGUE OF CULTURES

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Abstract

In psychology, ethnic identity is considered as one of the personality traits that is social in its consequences. Ethnic identity is the awareness of belonging to a certain ethnic community and isolation from other ethnic groups. Ethnic identity is the experience of one's identity with one ethnic community and separation from others. Ethnicity is defined by a number of objective indicators: the ethnicity of the parents, the place of birth, the language, culture. A person is most clearly aware of his ethnic identity in the process of interethnic communication, in a multicultural environment.

Keywords: ethnic identity, mono-ethnic identity, multiple identities, marginality, tolerance.

Considering the problem of ethnic identity, it is important to theoretically determine the correlation of this concept with the concept of ethnic self-consciousness. In modern literature, there are many views on the correlation of ethnic identity with ethnic self-consciousness (V.Y. Khotinets, G.U. Soldatova, V.N. Pavlenko, N.A. Shulga).

For example, T.G. Stefanenko proposes to consider ethnic identity not only as an individual's awareness of his belonging to a certain ethnos, but also as an experience of the relationship between the self and the ethnic environment, i.e., one's identity with one ethnic community and separation from others [1].

In Kazakhstan, this problem was studied by such scientists as Gabdulina K.G., Zheksembekova V.A., Burakanova G.M., Buribayeva G., etc.

Let us consider the typologies of ethnocultural identity.

In a multiethnic society, ethnic identity can manifest itself in several types:

1. Mono-ethnic identity with one's own ethnic group. People can more or less demonstratively maintain a positive group identity with their ethnic group. Depending on whether or not they are prejudiced against members of other ethnic groups and avoid close interaction with them, different subtypes of this identity can be distinguished.

2. Mono-ethnic identity with another ethnic group leads to complete assimilation, i.e. the adoption of the norms, customs, and language of the alien group, up to complete dissolution in it.

3. Multiple identities (e.g., biethnic) allow a person to use the experience of one group to adapt to another, to master the richness of another culture without compromising the values of his own. This has a beneficial effect on the personal growth of people from interethnic marriages.

4. Marginal ethnic identity – a person oscillates between two cultures without mastering either of them. Such people, confused about identities, often experience intrapersonal conflicts. They can be aggressive nationalists, either in favor of their own group or in favor of another group, depending on which of them has a higher status in society[2].

Marginality is also seen as belonging to two ethnic cultures at the same time, giving rise to a dual ethnic identity. It is typical for the descendants of ethnically mixed marriages, as well as for representatives of ethnic minorities included in a non-ethnic environment. Usually, marginality is accompanied by the idea of inequality of the social status of cultures and is psychologically expressed in the individual's awareness of his incomplete involvement in a "higher" culture and an incomplete break with the original "lower" one.

The meaning of each specific action often needs to be understood, because it does not always lie on the surface, but is most often hidden in traditional ideas of what is normal, which are also different in different cultures and socio-cultural groups. There is no universal "normal behavior".

Tolerance is a personal and social characteristic that presupposes the realization that the world and the social environment are multidimensional, varied, and therefore views on this world are different, and cannot

and should not be reduced to uniformity or in someone's favor (Tishkov, 1997). In the most general sense, tolerance is tolerance of any "otherness", within the framework of our topic, we speak of intercultural and interethnic tolerance [2].

Social distance characterizes the position of social groups and individuals in the social space, their correlation, that is, the level of their proximity or remoteness, alienation from each other, the degree of their interconnectedness.

In a 1926 study, Bogardus analyzed the responses of 1,725 Americans about their most acceptable distance from 40 racial and ethnic groups. Among the most preferred groups by Americans (average social distance from 1.06 to 1.83 points) were British, white Americans, Canadians and residents of Central and Northern Europe. A slightly higher social distance (from 1.94 to 2.47 points) was found in relation to residents of Southern and Eastern Europe. Americans distanced themselves the most from Easterners and blacks (2.69 to 3.91 points) (Bogardus, 1958).

In the 1940s, Hartley conducted a study of college students' attitudes toward 32 nationalities and races. He used the Bogardus Social Distance Scale, adding 3 fictional ethnic groups ("Danierreans", "Pireneans", "Wallonians") to the list of real ethnic groups. In the literature, this technique is called "Hartley's methodical method". It turned out that students who have prejudices against real groups are also wary of fictional groups. The correlation coefficients between preferred social distance for 32 real and three fictional groups were extremely high (0.80).

Here are some examples of respondents' comments. A student who exhibited intolerant attitudes toward many real-life groups said of fictional groups, "I don't know anything about them, but I would kick them out of my country." The tolerant respondent reasoned in the opposite way: "I know nothing about them, so I have no prejudices against them" (G.U. Soldatova, 1998) [3].

In modern socio-psychological and sociological studies of interethnic relations, the Bogardus scale continues to be one of the most popular methods. In particular, it was used by G. Soldatova in the study of interethnic attitudes among tolerant and intolerant respondents. It was found that a gradual increase in social distance from less significant to more significant types of contact among tolerant respondents contrasts with a sharp abrupt increase in social distance in the sphere of informal relations among intolerant respondents. For example, in the subgroup of tolerant Tatars, 80% of respondents are ready to accept a person of another nationality as a citizen of their republic, 72% as a neighbor, 35% as a spouse of their children, and 29% as a

marriage partner. At least 80% of respondents are also ready to see representatives of other ethnic groups as citizens of their republic, 64% are ready to see them as neighbors, but only 18% are already in the role of spouses of children, and 17% are ready to see them as their own spouses. This pattern turned out to be characteristic of other peoples as well (G.U. Soldatova, 1998).

A large number of observations and studies in the field of intercultural communication allow us to conclude that its content and results also largely depend on the values, norms of behavior, attitudes, etc., prevailing in a particular culture. Culture not only influences communication, but is itself influenced by it. Most often, this happens in the process of enculturation, when a person assimilates the norms and values of culture in one form or another of communication [4].

The processes of globalization and cultural dynamics, as practice shows, do not lead to the formation of a single world culture. Contemporary culture remains a multitude of distinctive cultures in dialogue and interaction with each other. Cultural change leads only to universalization, not to uniformity. But these processes force us to take a critical look at our own culture and the type of person inherent in it, to identify their intercultural boundaries. Modern studies of cultural anthropology show that the cultural identity of any people is inseparable from the cultural identity of other peoples, that all cultures are subject to the "laws" of communication. Therefore, the ability to understand other people's cultures and points of view, to critically analyze the reasons for one's own behavior, to recognize the cultural identity of others, to be able to incorporate other people's truths into one's position, to recognize the legitimacy of the existence of many truths, to be able to build dialogical relations and to make reasonable compromises are becoming increasingly important. The ongoing cultural changes are increasingly subject to the logic of cultural communication [5].

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